

H2020 – ICT-13-2018-2019

MUSKETEER

**Machine Learning to Augment Shared Knowledge in
Federated Privacy-Preserving Scenarios (MUSKETEER)**

Grant No 824988

D8.2 Dissemination and communication plan

May 19

Imprint

Contractual Date of Delivery to the EC: 31 May 2019

Author(s): Antoine Garnier (IDSA)

Participant(s): Karen McKenna (IBM)

Reviewer(s): Jaime Medina Maestro (Tree), Emil Lupu (IMP)

Project: Machine learning to augment shared knowledge in
federated privacy-preserving scenarios (MUSKETEER)

Work package: WP8

Dissemination level: Public

Version: 1.0

Contact: Antoine Garnier – antoine.garnier@internationaldatapaces.org

Website: www.MUSKETEER.eu

Legal disclaimer

The project Machine Learning to Augment Shared Knowledge in Federated Privacy-Preserving Scenarios (MUSKETEER) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824988. The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors.

Copyright

© MUSKETEER Consortium. Copies of this publication – also of extracts thereof – may only be made with reference to the publisher.

Executive Summary

The document provides a detailed view on the MUSKETEER's project activities about dissemination and communication. It highlights our strategy to reach the goals and KPIs written in the proposal. As a Research and Innovation Action, we expect to largely disseminate our results in the scientific community but also among various organizations interested or involved in the topics of the project. Therefore, our project combines external and internal means to disseminate and communicate the information among the partners and their networks. These two parts constitute the two main chapters of our deliverable described below.

Document History

Version	Date	Status	Author	Comment
1	01 Feb 2019	For internal review	Antoine Garnier	First draft
2	13 May 2019	Internal review	Jaime Medina	
3	20 May 2019	Internal review	Emil Lupu	
4	28 May 2019	Final review	IBM team	

Table of Contents

LIST OF FIGURES	5
LIST OF TABLES	5
LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	6
1 INTRODUCTION	7
1.1 Purpose.....	7
1.2 Related Documents	7
1.3 Document Structure	8
2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY	8
2.1 Value proposition.....	9
2.2 Targeted audience	9
2.3 Channels	10
2.3.1 Partner’s Networks.....	11
2.3.2 Events	12
2.3.3 Social media.....	12
2.3.4 Media.....	13
2.3.5 Scientific publications	13
2.4 Communication materials	14
2.5 Hackathon.....	16
3 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TRACKING PROCESS	16
3.1 Dissemination reporting.....	16
3.2 Internal communication	17
4 CONCLUSION	18
5 REFERENCES	18
6 ANNEX	19

6.1	Annex 1.....	19
6.2	Annex 2.....	20

List of Figures

Figure 1 Impact of Dissemination and Communication Plan on WP8 activities	7
Figure 2 MUSKETEER main outcomes.....	9
Figure 3 Business canvas model for the MUSKETEER platform	9
Figure 4 MUSKETEER brochure	15
Figure 5 Dissemination activities per organization	19
Figure 6 Aggregated list of dissemination activities of the MUSKETEER’s partners	20

List of Tables

Table 1 Targeted audiences for MUSKETEER project	10
Table 2 Different types of initiatives related to dissemination.....	17

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AECOC	Spanish Association of Manufacturers and Distributors
BIR	British Institute of Radiology
BMWi	German Federal Ministry of Economics and Energy
CLSR	Computer Law & Security Review
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
ECML	European Conference on Machine Learning
EEN	Enterprise Europe Network
ERRIN	European Regions R&I Network
EUM	End User Management
IAIPR	Impact Assessment Intellectual Property Rights
ICLR	International Conference on Learning Representations
ICML	International Conference on Machine Learning
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OWL	East Westphalia-Lippe (Germany)
PPP	European Public-Private Partnerships
PR	Public Relations
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
STRAEPT	Greek Society Of TEI 'S Medical Radiological Technologists
TNNLS	Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems
VDMA	German Machinery and Plant Engineering Association
WG	Working Group
ZVEI	Central Association of the Electrical Engineering and Electronics Industry e.V.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

The MUSKETEER main strategy is to raise attention on data sharing and widen the platform audience to new stakeholders in order to sustain the development of our industrial data ecosystem. The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) specifies the actions to disseminate and communicate the project results for the consortium in order to prepare the best exploitation phase possible.

The plan of this deliverable describes the general objectives to ensure the dissemination and communication of MUSKETEER project and activities for the overall project. This document will also be updated along the project.

1.2 Related Documents

The Dissemination and Communication Plan drives WP8 activities. It also influences several committees (described below) planned in the Proposal.

Figure 1 Impact of Dissemination and Communication Plan on WP8 activities

The Dissemination and Communication Plan:

defines the Project communication and engagement activities (D8.3)

defines the Scientific dissemination activities (D8.4)

defines the Community engagement and Technology Transfer activities (D8.5)

provide inputs for the Evaluation and impact assessment (D8.6)

The outcomes of the activities presented in deliverables D8.3, D8.4, D8.5 and D8.6 will **provide inputs** to adjust business plans and prepare the exploitation plan (D8.7).

WP8 activities have also relationships with several committees set up within the project.

The Impact Assessment IPR and Innovation Committee (IAIPR Committee) aims to take care of external request made to the consortium and concerning its activities. It includes demonstration, protection of the background and results, dissemination of data, access rights for third parties, joint ownership management, licensing agreements, protection of results or confidentiality, and market approach strategy, among others. On one side the activities of the IAIPR activities depends largely on the success of the communication & dissemination activities defines by D8.2, on the other side, D8.3, D8.4, D8.5 and D8.6 will report the IAIPR committee activities according to their targeted audience.

The End User Management Committee (EUM Committee) aims to coordinate end users and prepare the pilot scenarios before and during the validation phase. Among its tasks, it collaborates with the Dissemination Manager to promote the cooperation with other institutions and the adoption of the solutions developed in the project by external data providers. Those activities will be reported especially in D8.5.

1.3 Document Structure

The document is divided in two main sections. The first defines the dissemination and communication strategy. The second section describes the tracking process of those activities (tracking of partner's dissemination activities, information exchange).

2 Dissemination and communication strategy

In this section the dissemination and communication strategy will be addressed. The main objective of this strategy is to raise attention on the MUSKETEER platform and our research topics based on specific dissemination and communication actions. We also plan to leverage the partners' networks to circulate and advocate our work and products.

2.1 Value proposition

The main objective of the MUSKETEER project is to establish a secured and sustainable industrial data platform (machine learning over a high variety of different privacy-preserving scenarios) reinforcing the European leadership in Industrial Data Platforms tools.

Output mane	Type	Main author/s
MUSKETEER Architecture	Software	IBM
MUSKETEER Machine learning algorithms library	Software	TREE / UC3M
MUSKETEER mitigation and attack prevention algorithms and software	Software	IMP / IBM
Final prototype of MUSKETEER platform with client connectors	Software	ALL

Figure 2 MUSKETEER main outcomes

The figure above presents the main outcomes of the project. They will be used or directly implemented in the prototype. Therefore, the main goal of the dissemination and communication strategy will be directed at the promotion and the further exploitation of the MUSKETEER platform.

Key partners SMEs Large companies Other IDP initiatives Standardization organizations Data providers and data owners	Key activities Exploitation plan Dissemination activities Scientific communication	Value proposition Industrial Data Platform for extracting value from different data owners Unique privacy preserving and cybersecurity capabilities Includes Federated Machine Learning algorithms library	Customer relationship First “customers” inside the consortium (pilots) Assistance in the implementation of the platform Large customer network	Customer segments All organization that aims to exploit data and extract value from it.
	Key resources <u>Technical:</u> Data, Infrastructure, Data Scientists <u>Economic:</u> EC Funding, Partners equity, Business Angels		Channels Network of industrial consortium partners Data science communities BDVA	
Cost structure: Personnel costs, infrastructure costs, legal advice, communication activities.		Revenue Streams: Data providers: receive revenue depending on their dataset quality ; Data consumers: pay data providers depending on the usage of data made		

Figure 3 Business canvas model for the MUSKETEER platform

The MUSKETEER platform targets all organisations aiming at exploiting data as potential customers. Still, the consortium should be able to refine this proposition based on our use cases and different kind of outcomes the project will produce as described in the following section.

2.2 Targeted audience

Beyond the customer segment envisioned in the proposal for the platform (Figure 3), the different outcomes of MUSKETEER could reach a broader audience.

Table 1 Targeted audiences for MUSKETEER project

MUSKETEER Value Proposition						
Securing data exchange to foster the data economy development						
	Academ- ics	Standardi- zation bodies	Compe- tence cen- tres	SMEs & Mid-Caps	Large Compa- nies	Public bodies
Architecture	x	x			x	
ML algo- rithms li- brary	x	x	x		x	
Attack pre- vention algo. & soft.	x	(x)	x	x	x	x
Platform	(x)	(x)		x	x	x

As a Research and Innovative Action, our project’s outcomes target different categories of audiences. These publics have different interests and objectives that could be related to our results. The table above draws a clear picture for our different groups of interest depending on the subject to be treated. It then has to be associated to the different channels we plan to use to complete the picture.

Concerning “Attack prevention algorithms and software” and “Platform” we assume that Academics and Standardization bodies might have an interest, but not direct, as they are not potential customers of the algorithms and the platform. Nevertheless, they can offer a “multiplier effect”. With well-established connections in the rest of the value chain, they can participate to spread the word to stakeholders with direct interest such as SMEs or large companies, especially for the platform.

2.3 Channels

In order to develop our ecosystem beyond the sole partners of the consortium, MUSKETEER will use a combination of channels starting with the Partners’ networks (entities directly linked

to partners). Using the influence of the partners should help our project to get a greater attention in Europe. This is an essential part of the project. We will take advantage of the partners' communication and combine our dissemination and communication efforts with theirs. We plan to use their channels (events, social media, PR department, etc.) to disseminate our outcomes and reach the planned targets. We also have specific communication materials dedicated to the project (brochure, website) and plan to organize two *ad hoc* events, hackathons focused on our topics (privacy and security).

2.3.1 Partner's Networks

Partners' network refers to the organizations in which partners are directly represented (mostly on national and European levels). These channels will be used to widely disseminate the project activities in all ecosystems related to the project at EU and national level. We can consider the following networks:

European Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs), these associations which promote sectorial development will enable us to disseminate the project- through the partners that are members - , like ECSO (Cybersecurity PPP) or (BDVA Big Data Value PPP).

Sectoral Initiatives (in Manufacturing and Health sector):

- Manufacturing: several programs on national level related to Industry 4.0 concepts: Plattform Industrie 4.0, Mittelstand-Digital (BMW), DE.HUB Initiative (BMW), Standardization Council Industrie 4.0, Lab Network Initiative 4.0 in Germany; Industria Conectada 4.0 in Spain or Piano Industria 4.0 in Italy
- Others national manufacturing associations: German Mechanical and Plant Engineering Association (VDMA), German Electrical and Electronic Manufacturers' Association (ZVEI) in Germany or the Asociación Española de Fabricantes y Distribuidores (AECOC) in Spain
- Health: several national programs fostering innovation in healthcare are available such as the SBRI Healthcare Programme in the UK
- Others national health associations: The British Institute of Radiology (BIR) in the UK, the Greek Society of TEI's Medical Radiological Technologists (STRAEPT) or the Panhellenic Society of Radiotechnologists in Greece

Established open networks that will help us to reach out SMEs like the Enterprise Europe Network (EEN). Available in most European countries they offer national point of contact that we can request to raise attention of SMEs about our project.

And finally, **Regional Entities**, in manufacturing, health or more generally that deal with innovation topics like ERRIN (European Regions R&I Network), a Brussels based platform of more than 120 regional stakeholder's organisation that could help to facilitate transfer knowledge and support regional collaboration. They'll help the platform to gain new stakeholders on a regional basis based on the presentation of the use case either in manufacturing or health. Several regional clusters can be cited Digital Hub Logistics in Dortmund, Digital Hub Mobility in Munich, it's OWL Manufacturing Digitalisation (Nordrhein-Westfalen, Germany).

2.3.2 Events

MUSKETEER will take advantage of existing events, in which partners are exhibitors, to ensure the maximum impact. We will have 3 different lines of acting in terms of events as planned by the KPIs defined in the proposal:

10+ industrial diffusion events All the partners attend various fairs related to our fields of interest (security, big data, artificial intelligence, manufacturing, health). They will be requested to disseminate specifically the results of the project through such events (Cloud & Cyber Security Expo for security, Hannover Messe for Manufacturing or the European Society of Radiology for the Health (radiology) sector).

5 workshops / training sessions In accordance with the scientific dissemination and workshops related to the hackathons (see below), 5 workshops will be organized to discuss various concepts of the project such as data poisoning and possible defence strategies against them, federated learning to ensure data privacy or data sharing and sovereignty. It will enable to present some of our findings and also to get new feedback while developing the platform.

3 workgroups attendance Coordinated by tech development partners, the consortium will be able to disseminate its results and share its viewpoints in working groups of organizations related to security with partners' specialists (IBM, TREE, FCA) or data sharing. In this respect partners will present their results to the WG Architecture and/or Certification of IDS Association to ensure the compatibility of the platform. The association holds 4 meetings of each WG each year.

2.3.3 Social media

Our strategy for social media will integrate our Owned Media (LinkedIn, Twitter) and Shared Media (disposing with Partners' social media channels as detailed in Annex 2). The strategy adopted, using the different platforms, will target different targets/objectives:

- Twitter: for establishing MUSKETEER as an expert in privacy-preserving machine learning techniques related to data sharing increasing online

visibility and reaching out innovative companies and communicating with them 1:1 as potential new stakeholder.

- LinkedIn: to develop a community of expertise about privacy-preserving machine learning techniques to influence whole market and attract decision makers.

We will base our use of social media on Growth Hacking strategies that have proved to be most (cost) effective and efficient ways to grow a business. KPIs have already been defined concerning social media channels with the target of 1 post per week on average and +200 followers per account (Twitter and LinkedIn).

2.3.4 Media

Large media could have a limited interest for a project like MUSKETEER at first glance. Considering the efforts to gain their attention and their audience (general public), the work could seem to be pointless or at least not effective enough. Nonetheless MUSKETEER could target specialized media in the area of its use cases or scientific vulgarization media to raise the attention of specialists and innovation communities. With the help of PR services of the partners we will build the stories about our use cases, potential beneficiaries of the platform or our scientific results, to convince the journalists to publish such interesting stories. Potential media sources will include online medias' such as Industry Today or Manufacturing Global as well as trade magazines with the focus on manufacturing industry and/or business and European Radiology or Insight into Imaging for the health sector. This kind of relationship with the media, through a trustable and credible channel, is the most profitable way of disseminating nowadays, which will be supported by the strong relationship of the partners with the Media at regional Level. As defined by the proposal, we expect to reach 3 news releases per year. This material will be made available in our internal communication tool in order to be re-used by all the partners. It'll help us to present a common view when participating to an external event.

2.3.5 Scientific publications

As a Research and Innovation Action, we have a continuous scientific activity along the project. Our aim is to highlight the potential of technological innovation in order to drive adoption and facilitate realising the value of data. This should also be a way to draw more researchers towards addressing our challenges. Our strategy for scientific dissemination relies on three types of actions:

12 publications in conferences International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR), International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML), IEEE Symposium on Security & Privacy (S&P) or The European Conference on Machine Learning (ECML) on the European level have

been listed among important conferences to reach academic attention in the field of Machine learning or security. Our results will be submitted to such conferences. A more detailed view of the conferences we'll attend is available in Annex 1.

12 publications+ in JCR journals plenty of publications are dealing with our topics. Journal of Machine Learning Research, IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems (TNNLS), Computer Law & Security Review (CLSR) have been identified to reach an academic audience and also lawyers, ethicists (close to researchers in this field) and policy makers (in governments) when it comes to the security and privacy aspects of the project.

10 open source web community interactions such contact will help to disseminate our results but also to get feedback in the developing phase of the platform and to acquire new participants for the platform. Those contacts will be particularly developed in connexion with the hackathons. The main ambition of those events is to stress test the privacy and the security of the machine learning algorithms used in the platform. But when demonstrating the reliability of the platform, we will be able to recruit new stakeholders for our ecosystem. For instance, IDSA developers' community will be reached when testing the IDS compliancy of the MUSKETEER platform during the hackathon IDSA plans to organize. Its community, composed mainly of companies (SMEs and large corporate), should be interested to participate/join our emerging ecosystem. Our LinkedIn group, composed of researchers, developers or security experts should also help to raise attention about federated learning during the first months of the project. It should become an expert community to discuss our results. Eventually we will be committed to solve all issues reported in the open source repositories (linked to our activities) by the user's community in a timely manner. This also will contribute to disseminate our results and enlarge our ecosystem.

2.4 Communication materials

A visual identity has been defined in the first months of the project to give a specific branding of the project and the platform. It includes all the elements and styles to apply to the communication materials. A brochure has been produced to explain the project to specialists (it should be used for conferences and fairs but also to give a global idea of our activities to a broader public with a brief presentation of the project, its partners and contacts means. A target of 1000 copies has been defined to be distributed along the project.

CONSORTIUM

The MUSKETEER Consortium consists of 11 partners from all over Europe and combines experts from the technical, the research and the industrial sector:

- IBM
- TREX TECHNOLOGIES
- Imperial College London
- Engineering
- University Carlos III de Madrid
- INTERNATIONAL DATA SPACE ASSOCIATION
- INDUSTRIAL DATA PLATFORM
- FCA ITEM
- INRIA
- Biotronics 3D
- hygeia

MUSKETEER

info@musketeeer.eu

@H2020Musketeeer

H2020_MUSKETEER

MACHINE LEARNING TO AUGMENT SHARED KNOWLEDGE IN FEDERATED PRIVACY-PRESERVING SCENARIOS

www.MUSKETEER.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 624988.

MUSKETEER

The massive increase in data collected and stored worldwide calls for new ways to preserve privacy while still allowing data sharing in respect of their sovereignty among multiple data owners.

Today, the lack of usable trusted and secure environments for data sharing inhibits data economy while legality, privacy, trustworthiness, data value and confidentiality hamper the free flow of data.

MUSKETEER aims to create a validated, federated, privacy-preserving machine learning Industrial Data Platform (IDP) that is inter-operable, scalable and efficient enough to be deployed in real use cases.

MUSKETEER aims to alleviate data sharing barriers by providing secure, scalable and privacy-preserving analytics over decentralized datasets using machine learning based on IDSA concepts (architecture model and components). An initial set of privacy preserving machine learning algorithms to solve regression, classification and clustering problems will be provided, although the platform will be flexible enough to accept new algorithmic implementations.

Data can continue to be stored in different locations with different privacy constraints, but shared securely.

The **MUSKETEER** cross-domain platform will validate progress in the industrial scenarios of smart manufacturing and health.

MUSKETEER

The **MUSKETEER** mission is to develop an Industrial Data Platform with scalable algorithms for federated and privacy-preserving machine learning techniques, detection and mitigation of adversarial attacks, and a rewarding model capable of fairly monetizing datasets according to the real data value.

Objectives

1. Machine Learning over a high variety of different privacy-preserving scenarios.
2. Providing robustness against external and internal threats.
3. Enhancement of the Data Economy.
4. Providing a standardized and extensible architecture.
5. Industrial demonstration of the technology advances in operational environments.

For more information visit www.MUSKETEER.eu

Use Cases

MUSKETEER will validate its results in two specific use cases, however the final platform will be able to serve additional ones.

SMART MANUFACTURING
The project aims to collect and analyse automotive plant welding data, with the support of artificial intelligence technologies, to search for correlations among the variables that characterize the welding process so that the final welding point will be of the expected quality.

HEALTH
The project aims to demonstrate the application of the federated artificial intelligence approach, enabling access to vast amounts of distributed medical imaging data to train and improve the learning algorithms, providing powerful tools to improve clinical practice.

Privacy preserving approach

Every machine learning algorithm will use privacy techniques such as federated machine learning, differential privacy, homomorphic encryption or secure multiparty computation. Any other variable could be incorporated in the future thanks to the modular design of the platform.

MUSKETEER will support several Privacy Operation Modes (POMs) with different features:

- Privacy level.
- Computational local overload.
- Central Storage requirements.
- Communication requirements.
- Data Utility Accountability.

Figure 4 MUSKETEER brochure

Additionally, a website is available. To the attention of the specialists (academics, companies, etc.) to get a contact but also to the general public where the latest news of the project can be accessed, via Twitter and LinkedIn accounts. Brochure, scientific papers and public deliverables will be available online for easy downloading, making them accessible directly to interested audience throughout the world. The website should reach 3000 unique visitors along the project.

2.5 Hackathon

Two hackathons on Adversarial Attacks are planned along the project. Their main ambition is to stress test the privacy and the security of the machine learning algorithms used in the platform. Those events are powerful validation tools but also strong means of communication. They should raise attention about our work and results, but also enable us to recruit new stakeholders for the platform.

Hackathon will be advertised through our social media channels, but also during conferences or summer schools. They will be presented directly on security blogs (the hackernews.com, krebsonsecurity.com, etc.). Popular platforms such as Kaggle will be used to host our challenge reinforcing our online presence.

The results will be presented during a dedicated workshop (preferably during a machine learning conference). We plan to invite the winners of the hackathon to present a paper detailing their approach to poisoning the data. These workshops will be fully supported on our social media channels, website and through news release afterwards.

The two hackathons will be organized by TREE and IDSA.

3 Dissemination and Communication tracking process

3.1 Dissemination reporting

In order to get a maximum impact, dissemination and communication activities will be carried out in a timely manner with the development of the project in order to fully leverage project results and platform availability.

All partners and members of the ecosystem are requested to participate to the dissemination and communication actively, identifying all opportunities and collaborating with each other and external partners to foster the platform and results uptake. Active dissemination during the scientific and innovation events and promotion during European and national events will be monitored. It will help us to complete our KPIs as soon as possible.

For such purpose, we have designed a process, which objectives are:

- Early identification of possible dissemination and communication initiatives.
- Sharing related information with partners and identification of proper resources to conduct the dissemination.
- Reporting of results.

A Dissemination reporting excel (Annex 1) has been created for the consortium to provide an overview of the consortium's planned dissemination activities. The results will be communicated to the Impact Assessment IPR and Innovation Committee to adjust any required actions and to foster collaboration between partners (success stories, good practices, etc.). See Annex 1.

Table 2 Different types of initiatives related to dissemination

01. Online: Newsletter, email
02. Online: Website
03. Online: Social Media
04. Event: Workshops
05. Event: Trade show, exhibitions
06. Event: Conference
07. Event: Presentation / Lecture
08. Event: Hackathon
09. Publications: Conference papers
10. Publications: White papers
11. Publications: Scientific paper
12. Publications: Article / Interview (press, other media)
13. Liaisons with Innovation Actions
14. Liaisons with 3rd Parties
15. Liaisons with National Initiatives

3.2 Internal communication

The consortium is using Box-platform for internal documentation, revising and discussions. Dissemination materials, e.g. brochures, presentations, images etc. will be made available on

this platform for the consortium, as well as keeping project members up-to-date on dissemination opportunities.

The dissemination activities will be monitored by IDSA using two approaches: The Dissemination excel (annex 1) which gives an overview of the planned and done activities and the corrective action (if necessary) when the results will be presented to the Impact Assessment IPR and Innovation Committee as described above. Those activities and their results will be reported in this deliverable in deliverables 8.3 and 8.5 specifically.

4 Conclusion

First steps have already been achieved concerning dissemination and communication:

Produce communication materials for the consortium to disseminate and promote (M3):

- Communication Material for online channels, print and events.
- Set the social media channels.

We are now finalizing the Communication and Dissemination strategy (M6):

- Define targeted audiences and the communications channels.
- Describe the monitoring of progress and outcome of community activities by the consortium.
- Establish internal reporting of consortium's activities and impact.

Several deliverables will follow and report our Dissemination and Communication activities:

- D8.3 Project communication and engagement activities (M18).
- D8.4 Scientific dissemination activities (M36).
- D8.5 Community engagement and technology transfer activities (M36).

5 References

MUSKETEER LinkedIn account, <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8741148/>

MUSKETEER Twitter account, <https://twitter.com/H2020Musketeeer>

MUSKETEER Website, <http://musketeeer.eu/>

6.2 Annex 2

PARTNER	MUSKETEER TYPE	TITLE	ORGANIZER / PUBLISHER	DATE	PROJECT MONTH	COUNTRY	Link	NOTES/MOTIVATION/COMMENTS	STATUS
B3D	06 Event: Conference	ECR 2019	European Society of Radiology	28/02 - 03/03/2019	3	Austria	https://www.mysr.org/east-congress/eecr2019	B3D exhibited at ECR2019, the major event of radiology in Europe and 2nd worldwide, to present its products and research projects to Radiologists from all over the world.	Done
B3D	06 Event: Conference	Big Data and AI Tech World 2019	Closer Still	12/03/2019	4	UK	https://www.bigdataworld.com/conference-guests/mme	Big Data and AI Tech World are leading data events in UK. B3D visited the conference and disseminates its projects among participants.	Done
B3D	04 Event: Workshops	Spotlight on Ethics and Bias in AI for Healthcare	London Clinical and Health Data Science Meetup	16/03/2019	6	UK	https://www.meetup.com/lorclin/healthscilevents/219386551/	In order to fully realise the potential of these hugely powerful methods for healthcare, the ethical implications need to become a core part of how success is measured and an integral part of the deployment.	Planned
B3D	04 Event: Workshops	Welcome to the future of BigData!	Biometrics3D	24/05/2019	6	UK	www.biometrics3d.com	Celebrating 15 years, B3D will join customers together and present new products and research projects that may be integrated in future products.	Planned
B3D	06 Event: Conference	Big Data London	BigDataLond - 3rd Street Group	13-14/11/2019	12	UK	https://bigdataind.com/	Big Data LDN (London) is a free conference and exhibition, hosting leading data and analytics experts, with the tools to deliver most effective data-driven strategy.	Planned
B3D	06 Event: Conference	ECR 2020	European Society of Radiology	11-15/09/2020	16	Austria	https://www.mysr.org/congress/about-ecr	B3D plan to exhibit at ECR2020, the major event of radiology in Europe and 2nd worldwide, to present its products and research projects to Radiologists from all over the world.	Planned
B3D	06 Event: Conference	ECR 2021	European Society of Radiology	01/03/2021	28	Austria	https://www.mysr.org/congress/about-ecr	B3D plan to exhibit at ECR2021, the major event of radiology in Europe and 2nd worldwide, to present its products and research projects to Radiologists from all over the world.	Planned
COMAU	04 Event: Workshops	Internal workshop for requirements definition	COMAU	03/04/2019	4	Italy		Contacts collected among Comau colleagues and suppliers (Automation system, robotics, Bosh).	Done
COMAU	02 Online: Website	Comau web page	COMAU	31/05/2019	6	Italy	https://www.comau.com/en/this-is-comau/innovationdigitaltransformation/research-and-innovation-projects		Planned
COMAU	03 Online: Social Media	Musketeer project kick off	COMAU	06/01/2019	6	Italy			Planned
COMAU	04 Event: Workshops	Mid term Musketeer project achievements	COMAU	01/05/2020	18	Italy			Planned
ENG	06 Event: Conference	BDV meet up	ALL	26-28/06/2019	7	Latvia	http://www.bdv.eu/code/1317	BDV workshops with other projects under the PPP	Planned
ENG	06 Event: Conference	ICT proposers' day	ALL	19-20/9/19	10	Finland	https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/digital-excellence-forum-ict-proposers	Project dissemination in wide European forum	Planned
ENG	06 Event: Conference	European BDV forum	ALL	14-16/10/2019	11	Finland	http://www.big-data-hub.eu/code/1301/	Project dissemination in wide European forum, also required as we're part of the PPP	Planned
ENG	06 Event: Conference	BDVA Activity Group	BDVA	2/28/2019	3	Belgium		Musketeer presented to all BDVA Activity Group participants	Done
ENG	06 Event: Conference	BDV Steering Committee	BDVA	3/27/2019	3	Belgium		Attendance of the BDV PPP Steering Committee meeting	Done
FCA	04 Event: Workshops	Internal workshop 'as is analysis' and Musketeer objectives sharing	FCA ITEM	06/03/2019	4	ITALY			Done
FCA	04 Event: Workshops	Internal workshop Manufacturing Scenario - spot welding @ FCA	FCA ITEM	20/03/2019	4	ITALY			Done
FCA	03 Online: Social Media	Internal communication through Workplace by Facebook	FCA ITEM	07/06/2019	7	ITALY			Planned
IBM	04 Event: Workshops	AI Law & Ethics Conference	KU LEUVEN	28/02/2019	3	Belgium	https://www.kuleuven.be/ai/en/news/ai-law-ethics-conference-through-the-looking-glass-of-ai-at-forms-between-global-governance-and-techno-regulation-28-02	MUSKETEER flyer was presented at the event	Done
IBM	06 Event: Conference	BDV meet up	ALL	26-28/06/2019	7	Latvia	http://www.bdv.eu/code/1317	BDV workshops with other projects under the PPP	Planned
IBM	06 Event: Conference	ICT proposers' day	ALL	19-20/9/19	10	Finland	https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/digital-excellence-forum-ict-proposers	Project dissemination in wide European forum	Planned
IBM	06 Event: Conference	European BDV forum	ALL	14-16/10/2019	11	Finland	http://www.big-data-hub.eu/code/1301/	Project dissemination in wide European forum, also required as we're part of the PPP	Planned
IDS4	06 Event: Conference	Example (eXtreme) this: IDS4	IDS4	25-26/06/2019	6	Germany	http://www.big-data-hub.eu/code/1319/		Planned
IDS4	05 Event: Trade show exhibitions	Hannover Messe	Hannover Messe	01-05/04/2019	4	Germany	https://www.hannovermesse.de/home	Exhibitor (presentation of MUSKETEER among IDS4 activities)	Planned
IDS4	06 Event: Conference	IDS4 Summit	IDS4	25-26/06/2019	6	Germany	https://www.internationaldatapaces.org/	Annual presentation of IDS4 activities	Planned
IDS4	06 Event: Conference	High Tech Event	IDS4	27/02/2019	2	Germany		Update IDS4 activities with national authorities	Planned

Figure 6 Aggregated list of dissemination activities of the MUSKETEER's partners

The document is also accessible on Box here: <https://app.box.com/folder/72371916537>